

TEACHER'S PEDAGOGICAL SKILLS

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Abstract. This study highlights the importance of teachers' pedagogical skills in the modern education system, the need for educators to be consistent with modern educational standards, and at the same time, provide guidelines for improving their methodology, thereby improving the level of knowledge of students and the quality of education.

Keywords: Methodological and teaching aids, professional, pedagogical ability, adequacy, professional potential, individual activity, pedagogical intellect.

O'QITUVCHINING PEDAGOGIK MAHORATI

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqot davomida zamonaviy ta'lim tizimida o'qituvchilarning pedagogik mahoratni ahamiyati, pedagoglarning zamonaviy ta'lim standartlarida tayyorlangan bo'lishi, shu asnoda metodikasini oshirish va shu orqali o'quvchilarning bilim darjasini, ta'lim sifatini oshirish uchun ko'rsatmalar berib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Metodik va o'quv qo'llanmalari, professional, pedagogik qobiliyat, adekvatlik, kasbiy salohiyat, individual faoliyat, pedagogik intellekt.

ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ МАСТЕРСТВА УЧИТЕЛЯ

Аннотация. В данном исследовании подчеркивается важность педагогического мастерства учителей в современной системе образования, необходимость соответствия педагогов современным образовательным стандартам и в то же время предоставления рекомендаций по совершенствованию своей методологии, тем самым повышая уровень знаний учащихся и качество образования.

Ключевые слова: методические и учебные пособия, профессиональный, педагогическое мастерство, адекватность, профессиональный потенциал, индивидуальная активность, педагогический интеллект.

Introduction

What should a modern teacher be like? After independence, this problem became the focus of attention of many scientists, intellectuals, and even parents. Modern, up-to-date methodological and educational manuals and textbooks began to be created for teachers. However, research and scientific studies on this problem continue to this day. Today's global changes, the daily development of science, technology, and information and communication

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technologies require a 21st century teacher to have pedagogical skills, a sharp will, pedagogical and psychological knowledge, deep knowledge of his subject and high thinking, political literacy, and a broad and thoughtful range of thinking. Teachers working in educational institutions must be well-versed in the optimal organization of teaching forms and the enrichment of the theory of the formation of a harmonious personality with various new ideas. After all, the implementation of the ideas of the "National Personnel Training Program" into practice, ensuring the success of the reforms being carried out in the education system of our country, largely depends on the spiritual image and professional skills of teachers and educators working in educational institutions. The important aspects of reforms in the field of education that can meet the requirements of today's changing times are their coherence and integrity in content. Our government attaches great importance to restoring our great spirituality of the past and raising education and upbringing to the level of modern requirements. Our homeland and society need specialists who can think, are cultured and knowledgeable in their field. In particular, a specialist is required to be a skilled master of his profession. A true professional is always in development and is considered a researcher throughout his entire working life. In particular, independent education and methodological activity have a great influence on the formation of professionalism in a teacher. The main criteria for the professionalism of a teacher are also known to everyone. These are: good knowledge of the methodology and its improvement; good knowledge of the psychology of students in order to organize effective interaction; good knowledge of the subject he teaches and constant research on it, self-improvement. Pedagogical activity is the labor activity of specially trained specialists who are responsible before the people and the state to prepare the younger generation for life and work. Pedagogical skills. A teacher must have pedagogical skills in order to work successfully. A person with pedagogical skills achieves great results with little effort. Creativity is always his companion. Pedagogical ability. Ability appears and develops in the process of activity. Teaching skills are the art of teaching and upbringing. This is a professional skill that directs all types of educational work to the comprehensive development of the student, including his worldview and abilities. Externally, it is manifested in the successful creative solution of various pedagogical tasks, in the effective achievement of methods and goals of educational work. Its more specific external indicators are: a high level of work, the quality of the teacher's work; appropriate actions of the teacher, adequate to pedagogical situations; achievement of results in the training, upbringing and independent work of students; independent acquisition of knowledge, development of the ability to acquire knowledge, involvement in independent

scientific research. Internally, pedagogical skill is a functional system of knowledge, skills, abilities, mental processes and personal characteristics that ensure the implementation of pedagogical tasks. In this regard, pedagogical skill is a manifestation of. The content of the process of developing the teacher's pedagogical skill includes: the teacher's professional potential and stability, components and criteria of pedagogical skill. The most important point in the teacher's activity is professional potential. This is the ability and opportunity to perform their work at the level of modern requirements provided by the teaching profession, in harmony with the style of educational and educational activity. The composition of a teacher's professional potential consists of the following characteristics: - the teacher's professional skills (humanistic attention to students, innovations in the educational process, professional growth and position); - pedagogical culture (thinking style, teaching techniques, communication skills, social skills, methods); - professional training (pedagogical intelligence, individual style of activity, creative attitude to work, competence).

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be said that in the world, large-scale work is being carried out to train pedagogical personnel, develop mechanisms and technologies for improving the organization of education. At the same time, it is noted that there is a need to form modern teaching methodologies among teachers, increase the use of new technologies in explaining lessons to students, and "improve the process and tools for assessing the quality of education, and implement mechanisms that allow determining the achieved results."

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